

USING MOBILE GAMES TO ENHANCE LANGUAGE TEACHING AND LEARNING FOR MIDDLE SCHOOL LEARNERS: STRATEGIES FOR BLENDED LEARNING

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Abstract. Today, technology is creating a significant transformation in the field of education. Mobile games, in particular, stand out as an effective tool to increase young students' interest in language learning and to improve their learning processes. While secondary school students are growing up in a rapidly changing digital world, they benefit from the learning opportunities offered by mobile applications. In this article, the role of mobile games in language teaching and learning will be discussed together with blended learning strategies and best practices will be presented in this process.

Key words. Mobile games, motivation, blended learning, feedback.

The role of mobile games in language teaching:

Participation and motivation:

Mobile games enable students to actively participate in the learning process and increase their interest and motivation for knowledge. The entertaining nature of games makes the learning environment more attractive, which leads students to put more effort into improving their language skills. Research shows that mobile games significantly increase students' learning motivation.

Interactive learning environment:

Mobile games provide interactive learning experiences. These games encourage students to learn both individually and in groups. For example, multiplayer mobile games provide opportunities for students to practice language

skills by encouraging collaboration and competition among students. Students have the opportunity to develop their language skills while interacting with each-other.

Individualized learning:

Mobile games allow students to learn at their own pace. Each student has a different learning style and pace. Mobile games provide personalized learning experiences, allowing students to respond their own needs. This results in more permanent and effective language learning.

Instant feedback: Students can receive instant feedback on their learning process through mobile games. This allows them to immediately correct their mistakes and evaluate their progress. By learning from their mistakes, students can realise which areas they need to improve. This feature increases their self-assessment skills and allows students to manage their learning processes more actively.

Blended learning is a teaching model that combines face to face education with online learning. Mobile games can be used effectively in blended learning environments. Here are some strategies to consider in this process:

Integrated game selection: It is important to integrate mobile games into the curriculum. Appropriate games should be selected to improve students' language skills. Focusing on the vocabulary, grammar rules and communication skills of the target language makes an important contribution to the teaching process.

Pre- and post-game activities: Organising activities before and after the game helps students consolidate what they have learned. Goals should be set before the game, active participation should be ensured by assigning specific tasks during the game, and the information they have learned should be discussed after the game. This process allows students to evaluate their experiences and increase their metacognitive awareness.

Student feedback: Student feedback should be obtained to evaluate how mobile games are used in the teaching process. This feedback is important to improve teaching process. This feedback is important to improve teaching methods and evaluate their whether the game is effective. When students express their

opinions about the game, they should be encouraged to ask which games are more useful to them.

Social learning: Students should be encouraged to work in groups while playing games. Team-based activities allow students to help each-other and practice their language. Communicating with friends supports language learning as well as developing social skills.

In conclusion, mobile games stand out as an effective way to support language teaching and learning for secondary school students. Games help students develop their language skills by providing interactive, fun and personalized learning experiences. The integration of mobile games with blended learning strategies enriches the educational processes and enables students to participate more actively in learning. Educators can make students' language learning more effective by integrating mobile games into their lessons.

REFERENCES

1. Gonzalez, T. (2016). Mobile learning in higher education: The role of the teacher and learning design. *Educational technology & Society*, 19 (3), 10-20.
2. Hattie, J&Timperley, H (2007). The power of feedback. *Review of educational research*, 77(1), 81-112.
3. Kapp,K.M. (2012). *Gamification of learning and instruction: Game-based methods and strategies for training and education*. John Wiley& Sons.
4. Squire, K. (2005). Changing the game: What happens when video games enter the classroom? *Innovate: Journal of online education*, 1(6).